

Laura Vela-Plo*

Phrasal subcomparatives: a comparative coordination analysis based on evidence from Basque, Spanish, and English

<https://doi.org/10.1515/ling-2022-0001>

Received January 2, 2022; accepted February 19, 2022; published online January 2, 2023

Abstract: By analyzing an understudied type of comparative, namely, subcomparatives with surface-phrasal standards of comparison, this article offers an answer to three long-debated questions regarding the internal structure and semantic composition of comparative constructions in opposition to traditional assumptions and reductionist analyses. First I offer syntactic tests evidencing the non-clausal status of the standard in these subcomparatives in Basque, Spanish and English. Second, regarding the question of the linkage type between the compared elements (either a dependence relation or a coordination relation), I present previous and novel syntactic evidence showing that phrasal subcomparatives invariably behave like common phrasal coordinates. Therefore, I defend an architecture of these comparatives involving a phrasal coordinate structure and offer a transparent mapping between the surface syntax and semantic interpretation of these constructions. Third, subcomparatives involve the obligatory omission of a measure modifier from the standard. This process known as *comparative subdeletion* cannot be explained as the result of *wh*-movement within a clause, given the non-clausal status of the standard. Alternatively, comparative subdeletion is defined not as an *ad hoc* deletion rule but rather as the result of an obligatory deletion operation independently attested in common coordinate structures.

Keywords: Basque; comparative subdeletion; coordination; English; phrasal standard; Spanish; subcomparatives

1 Introduction

The term *subcomparative* was introduced by Bresnan (1973, 1975) to refer to sentences that compare quantities or degrees of different sorts of stuff and in which,

*Corresponding author: Laura Vela-Plo, Micaela Portilla Research Center, Office 3.7, University of the Basque Country, HiTT, Justo Vélez de Elorriaga 1, 01006 Vitoria-Gasteiz., Spain, E-mail: laura.vela@ehu.eus. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3368-8548>

Open Access. © 2022 the author(s), published by De Gruyter. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.